

SPIRAL PROGRESSION IN SCIENCE: ITS VOLATILITIES, UNCERTAINTIES, COMPLEXITIES, AND AMBIGUITIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11231231>

ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to determine the teachers' perception of the Spiral Progression in Science in terms of its volatilities, uncertainties, complexities, and ambiguities and its impact on the teachers' performance in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy. The respondents of this study are 42 Junior High School Science Teachers, 23 Secondary School Heads, and 407 Junior High School Students. Two types of modified questionnaires which have undergone validation and reliability testing were used in gathering the data. Statistical tools used in the study were Weighted mean, Spearman Rank Correlation, ANOVA, and Kruskal-Wallis Test. The results revealed that science teachers "Somewhat Agree" on the Volatilities, Uncertainties, Complexities, and Ambiguities of the SPA. Teachers were found to be competent with "High" and "Very High" levels of performance across all strands of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy in the PPST. Furthermore, the data revealed a significant relationship between the teachers' perception of the spiral progression in science and their performance in terms of volatilities. Moreover, it was found that there is no significant difference in the performance of the teachers when they are grouped according to their profile. Consequently, there is no significant difference in the perceptions of the teachers on the SPA in Science when they are grouped according to their profile.

Keywords: *Spiral Progression in Science, VUCA, Teacher Performance, Content Knowledge and Pedagogy*

INTRODUCTION

The spiral progression approach in education, which is based on Bruner's Constructivist theory of learning in 1960, has long been implemented (Dunton & Co, 2019). This is a strategy formulated to help students develop their thinking and problem-solving abilities, which can then be applied across a variety of concepts rather than simply imparting knowledge to them (Joseph, 2021). Throughout the years, the spiral approach in curriculums has proven to be advantageous in terms of promoting the motivation and achievement of students (Hamlen & Chu, 2023). However, Paring et al. (2021) identified drawbacks in this approach such as frequent introduction of ideas either too quickly or too slowly. On the other hand, science education plays a vital component in the world of volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity (VUCA) (Sinha & Sinha, 2020). VUCA describes the complex, advancing, and dynamic environment brought about by various challenges faced throughout the years (Waller et al., 2019).

The Philippine Education system at present, specifically in the Grades 1-10 curriculum, follows the spiral progression approach anchored in Republic Act 10533 or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (Bug-os et al., 2021). Since its implementation, Science Education in the Philippines has fallen behind other countries (Sadera et al., 2020). The Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) showed that students in the Philippines ranked 78th out of 79 countries in Science and Math (OECD, 2019). In the 2022 OECD rankings, Filipino learners were placed 79th out of 81 countries in science proficiency (OECD, 2023). These rankings emphasize the pressing need for enhancements in the Philippine educational system and curriculum. This is to cultivate an educational environment that nurtures students capable of excelling not only in domestic but also in global assessments. According to Driscoll (2021), quality learning is dependent on high-quality teaching, achieved through improving the teacher's knowledge of content and pedagogy.

In line with this, the researcher found it important to assess teachers' VUCA in implementing the spiral progression in science and find out whether these affect their capability in teaching when talking about content knowledge and pedagogy. Currently, many studies related to VUCA have been conducted. For instance, the study of Baron and Dela Cruz (2023) on VUCA in Philippine Education is centered on the implementation of the spiral progression rather than investigating how teachers' perception of VUCA could affect their performance in the classrooms. Moreover, the study of De Ramos-Samala (2018) mainly dealt with the underlying factors connected with the adoption of the spiral implementation in science. VUCA, in relation to teachers' pedagogical content knowledge and performance in the classroom, remains not well-explored.

With this, the researcher would want to investigate how the teachers' VUCA perception of the spiral progression in science affects their performance in the classroom. Furthermore, this study would aim to better understand the VUCA of spiral progression to further improve the performance of teachers in Bais City Division in terms of science content knowledge and pedagogy.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the teachers' perception of the spiral progression in teaching science in terms of its volatilities, uncertainties, complexities, and ambiguities and its impact on their performance in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy. The results of this study would serve as the basis for the formulation of a lesson exemplar in Science 7, which shall be anchored on the MATATAG Curriculum of DepEd.

Specifically, this study sought to address the following questions:

1. What is the science teachers' perception of the spiral progression approach of K to 12 program in terms of its:
 - 1.1 volatilities;
 - 1.2 uncertainties;
 - 1.3 complexities; and
 - 1.4 ambiguities?
 2. What is the level of teachers' performance in content knowledge and pedagogy in science in as perceived by the students and school heads?
 3. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' perception of the spiral progression in science and their performance?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational design. The descriptive design provides a view of the current scenario happening in the research environment (Stangor & Walinga, 2019). It is also correlational due to its purpose of looking into the relationship between the teachers' perception of the SPA in science and their performance.

Research Environment

This study was conducted in Bais City Division, located in Bais City, Negros Oriental Philippines. The division is composed of forty-one (41) complete elementary schools, sixteen (16) Secondary Schools, and ten (10) Integrated Schools.

Research Respondents

The respondents for this study were the 42 junior high school science teachers of Bais City Division. Each teacher was assessed by 10 randomly chosen students and one School Head/Instructional Supervisor. In this study, there are 407 students in total to rate the teachers. The teachers completed a questionnaire related to the Spiral Progression in Science (SPA), while the students and school heads provided evaluations of the teachers' performance in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy.

Research Instruments

This study utilized questionnaires that were modified from various related studies: the first set of questionnaires is intended to gather perceptions from secondary science teachers in terms of VUCA of the spiral progression approach to teaching science, modified from the study of Baron and Dela Cruz in 2023 while the second set is for the students and school heads who would rate the performance of science teachers in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy which contains some indicators adopted from the study of Eraga (2021) and Sedillo (2021). The researcher asked permission from the authors through email to utilize the research instruments.

To assure the validity of these questionnaires, the researcher consulted three (3) experts, upon the approval of the Foundation University Graduate School, to review the contents. To test the reliability of the questionnaire on assessment of the teachers' VUCA perception, a dry run was conducted on teachers who were not part of the sample. The gathered data were treated using Cronbach's Alpha test to determine the reliability of each indicator in which the values computed were found to be greater than 0.70, thereby proving that the items are reliable.

Research Procedure

After the design hearing, the researcher incorporated all the necessary corrections and suggestions given by the panel members. A letter of request stating the intent to conduct the study was submitted to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Bais City upon the endorsement of the dean of the graduate school of Foundation University. The signed and approved letter of intent was presented to the different school administrators within the scope of the study. During the distribution, the researcher thoroughly explained, in writing, the purpose and significance of the study. Retrieval of the questionnaires was done after the respondents answered the questions. Results gathered were processed using Microsoft Excel and online calculators for the analysis and interpretation of data.

Scope and Limitations

This research is intended to investigate the science teachers' perception of VUCA of the Spiral Progression Approach to science teaching and how their perception affects their performance in class in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy. This study is limited to the junior high school science teachers' views in terms of VUCA and the impact of their views on their content knowledge and pedagogy. The teachers' content knowledge and pedagogy were measured primarily through the students' and school heads' perceptions of the teacher's practices during classes. Other variables affecting or contributing to the teachers' performance were not included in this paper.

RESULTS

Table 1.1 Perception of the Science Teachers on the SPA of K to 12 in terms of its Volatilities (n=42)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD
1. I noticed that learners' retention and mastery of topics and skills are not strengthened as they are revisited.	5.38	A
2. The school lacks necessary teaching and learning materials such as textbooks, ICT equipment, and laboratory equipment.	5.38	A
3. This approach lacks continuity of contents since there is no constant repetition, review, and reinforcement of learning.	4.93	SoA
4. I observed that some of the knowledge learned from the previous lesson does not serve as prerequisites for the succeeding lesson.	4.38	NAD
5. I find it problematic because there is no logical arrangement of content.	4.31	NAD
6. The use of differentiated instructions to cater to learners' diverse ways of learning is disregarded in this approach.	3.98	NAD
7. The teaching methods frequently used do not balance teaching skills and science knowledge.	3.93	NAD
8. Some topics are not relevant to students' development/cognitive stages for this grade level.	3.36	SoD
Composite	4.46	SoA

Table 1.1 presents the perception of the science teachers on the spiral progression in terms of its volatilities. Generally, the teachers "somewhat agree" on the volatilities of the spiral progression in science as evidenced by the value of the composite weighted mean of 4.46. The findings indicates that the spiral progression in science does not strengthen learners' retention and mastery of the concepts.

Table 1.2 Perception of the Science Teachers on the SPA of K to 12 in terms of its Uncertainties (n=42)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD
1. The time allotted (budget of work) for teaching specific competencies are not enough in mastering a topic.	5.31	A
2. Many topics are covered but are taught only briefly wherein many students fail to master important concepts	5.29	A
3. Since they are non-negotiable, competencies hinder growth opportunities to learn, unlearn and relearn concepts.	4.36	SoA
4. The integration of DepEd TV video lessons is not enough to develop students' basic skills in science.	4.26	NAD
5. Recommended performance tasks provided cannot be equated to valid experiences.	4.24	NAD
6. This approach does not strengthen retention as competencies are paired with a specific performance task.	4.14	NAD
7. Content standards are not sufficient to prevent misunderstanding.	4.00	NAD

8. The competencies are not flexible for change; thus, it is not future proof.	3.98	NAD
Composite	4.45	SoA

Table 1.2 depicts the perception of the Science teachers on the Spiral Progression in Science in terms of its uncertainties. In general, the teachers “somewhat agree” with the uncertainties presented as evidenced by the value of the composite weighted mean of 4.45.

Table 1.3 Perception of the Science Teachers on the SPA of K to 12 in terms of its Complexities (n=42)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD
1. The process is time-consuming because I often need to review prerequisite materials before proceeding with the intended lesson, given that many students have already forgotten them.	5.50	A
2. It is difficult to teach using this approach because all concepts are allotted the same amount of time whether they are easy or difficult to master.	5.12	SoA
3. The content standard allotted per year level is limited and problematic because the focus is very minimal, lacks depth, and lacks concentration.	4.90	SoA
4. This approach does not give the students a chance to apply and develop their skills and understanding in an increasingly challenging situation.	4.71	SoA
5. I observed that it is difficult for the students to connect their previous lesson to the next one because some level of subject matter is not well connected to the next.	4.64	SoA
6. The progression of learning competencies in science does not cater to learners’ needs for a particular period.	4.36	NAD
7. It does not provide a concrete link between concepts.	4.00	NAD
Composite	4.75	SoA

Table 1.3 reveals science teachers’ perception of the spiral progression in science in terms of its uncertainties. Generally, the teachers “somewhat agree” with the complexities of the spiral progression in science ($w\bar{x}= 4.75$).

Table 1.4 Perception of the Science Teachers on the SPA of K to 12 in terms of its Ambiguities (n=42)

Indicators	w \bar{x}	VD
1. The usefulness of content is relative to the learner who is going to use it.	5.12	SoA
2. Teachers do not have expertise on all topics covered in science.	5.00	SoA
3. In this approach, the presentations of the lessons are not broadened and deepened each time a concept is revisited.	4.81	SoA
4. The students do not learn the subject matter in their pace.	4.69	SoA
5. The lessons are not extended in a more elaborate and comprehensive teaching style.	4.64	SoA
6. The teaching strategies frequently used such as lectures and class discussions does not help learners appreciate the connections among the different content standards.	4.45	SoA
7. Assessment method is not really fixed in all approaches thus, it is hard to gather authentic learning from students.	4.40	NAD
8. The suggested performance tasks in the MELCs does not provide relevance and real-world experience to create stronger connections to the content that is to be covered.	4.02	NAD
Composite	4.64	SoA

Table 1.4 reveals the perception of science teachers on the spiral progression of the K-12 science curriculum in terms of ambiguities. Generally, the respondents “somewhat agree” with the ambiguities of the spiral progression as manifested in the value of the composite weighted mean of 4.64.

Table 2. Level of Teachers’ Performance in Science in Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Indicators	Students (n=407)		School Heads (n=42)	
	w \bar{x}	LoP	w \bar{x}	LoP
1. Content knowledge and pedagogy and its application within and across curriculum	6.06	H	6.24	VH
2. Research-based knowledge and knowledge and principles of teaching and learning	6.07	H	5.98	H
3. Positive use of ICT	5.67	H	5.56	H
4. Strategies in promoting literacy and numeracy	5.86	H	6.08	H
5. Strategies for developing critical, creative, and higher order thinking skills	6.00	VH	6.16	VH
6. Application of mother tongue (Sinugbuanong Bisaya), Filipino, and English	6.06	VH	6.28	VH
7. Classroom communication strategies	6.12	VH	6.28	VH
Overall	5.98	H	6.08	H

Table 2 reveals an overview of the science teachers' performance across domain 1: content knowledge and pedagogy.

Table 3. Relationship between the Teachers' Perception of the Spiral Progression in Science and Their Performance (n = 42)

Variables Correlated to Performance	r_s	p-value	Decision	Remark
Volatilities	-0.338	0.029	Reject H_{01}	Significant
Uncertainties	-0.128	0.423	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Complexities	-0.013	0.937	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Ambiguities	-0.077	0.627	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant

Level of significance = 0.05

Table 3 reveals the data in identifying the relationship between the teachers' perception of the SPA in Science and their performance. The data reflect that teachers' perception of the volatilities of spiral progression in science is significantly and inversely related to their performance ($r_s = -0.338$; $p = 0.029$). The negative sign indicates that teachers with better performance perceive the volatilities of SPA in science to a lower level.

DISCUSSION

Perception of Science Teachers on the Volatilities of Spiral Progression of the K-12 Program

A The findings indicate that the spiral progression in science does not strengthen learners' retention and mastery of the concepts. According to Dagasaan (2022), the spiral progression introduces new ideas quickly and rapidly. Tapanan et al. (2021) observed the same trend and concluded that quick discussion of topics resulted in students' low retention and mastery of the concepts, and this might be caused in a potential gap in teaching strategies. This agrees with Paring et al. (2021), who acknowledged that there is a problem of acquiring previous knowledge because students could not recall concepts from their previous science subjects.

However, the study of Shariati et al. (2021) contradicts the current finding by claiming that the spiral progression results in a thorough understanding of concepts and strengthened long-term memory, which could be considered indicators of increased academic performance.

Further, the result also suggests that schools lack the necessary equipment, facilities, and resources which could be considered as factors that may hinder productive teaching and learning processes. According to Baron and Dela Cruz (2023), quality output was observed in schools with functional facilities. Similarly, Twizeyimana et al.

(2020) stated that inadequate resources would result in a poor implementation of the Science Curriculum.

The data also reveals that the teachers “somewhat agree” that the SPA lacks continuity of contents since there is no constant repetition, review, and reinforcement of learning. This implies that students will be challenged in learning new concepts since one feature of this approach is to build new knowledge based on previously learned concepts. This result, however, contradicts the key features of spiral progression in education, which include constant revisiting of topics, increasing complexities, and acquisition of knowledge based on prior knowledge (Tirol, 2022). This further indicates that the current implementation of the Philippines’ science education needs further review, as Sadera et al. (2020) described it to be “ailing.”

Perception of Science Teachers on the Uncertainties of Spiral Progression of the K-12 Program

The data specifically discloses that teachers “agree” that in the spiral progression in science, the time allotted (budget of work) for teaching specific competencies is not enough to master a topic. Consequently, the teachers also “agree” that many topics are covered but are taught only briefly so that many students fail to master important concepts. According to Tapanan et al. (2021), teachers would skip difficult lessons and proceed to easier ones to finish their budget of work.

The results imply science teachers’ agreement that due to insufficient time allocated to cover competencies and a gap in the teaching-learning process, students would struggle to grasp the concepts, and thus it impedes their mastery of the topics. It was also noted by Paring et al. (2021) who assert that spiral progression does not promote sufficient review once competencies are covered. However, in a study conducted by Garcia (2021), the results suggest that teachers are given enough time to discuss different topics within the year to warrant that students can fully master the content. On a similar note, the study of Batidor and Casinillo (2021) and Igcasama (2021) unveiled that spiral progression ensures continuous reviews and progression, which will guarantee mastery after completion of the previous level.

Furthermore, the teachers “somewhat agree” that the competencies are non-negotiable, and therefore, hinder the growth opportunities for students to learn, unlearn and relearn concepts. This contrasts with the study of Tirol (2022), who posited that progression and continuity are the central themes in science education. This means that this spiral progression includes planned and projected outcomes and that once the fundamental topics are mastered, there is a reinforcement of what has been learned and a rich and profound understanding is attained.

Perception of Science Teachers on the Complexities of Spiral Progression of the K-12 Program

Gleaned from the result, teachers “agree” that the process is time-consuming because there is a need to review prerequisite materials before proceeding with the intended lesson. This is congruent with the study of Nahine et al. (2024) who postulated that the spiral progression requires overemphasis on reviewing and that it offers insufficient review time. Similarly, De Ramos-Samala (2018) claimed that spiral progression is time-consuming and there is repetition of topics across grade levels.

The science teachers “somewhat agree” that the spiral progression is difficult to use in teaching because all concepts are allotted the same amount of time whether they are easy or difficult ($w\bar{x}= 5.12$), and mastery of content standard allotted per year level is limited and problematic because the focus is very minimal, lacks depth, and lacks concentration ($w\bar{x}= 4.90$). Moreover, teachers also “somewhat agree” that this approach does not give the students a chance to apply and develop their skills and understanding in an increasingly challenging situation ($w\bar{x}= 4.71$) and is difficult for the students to connect their previous lesson to the next one because some level of subject matter is not well connected to the next ($w\bar{x}= 4.64$).

The result means that the spiral progression in science poses a challenge to junior high school science teachers because of its equal teaching time allocation to concepts regardless of their complexity. Also, the respondents claim that the spiral progression is limiting and lacking in depth and so it does not provide an opportunity for students to apply and develop skills in a more challenging way. These observations are parallel to the idea of Paring et al. (2021) that spiral progression features coverage of a topic in just a short amount of time resulting in students’ failure to understand concepts. Additionally, Perez et al. (2020) claimed that spiral progression lacks depth and concentration for each of the components of science. In fact, they have that some of the fundamental concepts in science are omitted in the spiral progression approach. This leads to the lack of mastery of prior topics coupled with less anchored concepts resulting in difficulties to understand concepts in the succeeding science levels.

The usefulness of content depends on the learners. This pertains to students’ uniqueness in learning, considering their learning styles and habits, and their willingness to learn (Garcia, 2021). This becomes an ambiguity and a factor in learning science because what works for one student may not be as effective for others. This emphasizes the importance of modifying the competencies to fit the specific needs of each learner.

Perception of Science Teachers on the Ambiguities of Spiral Progression of the K-12 Program

The science teachers “somewhat agree” with indicators 1 to 6 with weighted means ranging from 4.45 to 5.12: a) the usefulness of content is relative to the learner who uses it; b) teachers do not have expertise in all topics covered in science; c) presentations of the lessons are not broadened and deepened each time a concept is

revisited; d) students do not learn the subject matter in their pace; e) lessons are not extended in a more elaborate and comprehensive teaching style; and that f) the teaching strategies frequently used such as lectures and class discussions do not help learners appreciate the connections among the different content standards. The results suggest that teachers view the spiral progression in science as somewhat ambiguous and that there are concerns involving the relative usefulness of the content to learners, teachers' expertise in the different branches of science needed to be taught, the pacing of learning, and the style of teaching appropriate for the learners at hand.

Another concern of spiral progression as revealed in the data is the teachers' expertise in teaching different branches of science. Teachers "somewhat agree" that they do not have expertise in teaching all the topics covered in science. This concern agrees with the statement of Bug-os et al. (2021) that some teachers tend to favor one area over the others. As a matter of fact, Gonzales (2019) reported that teachers were having a hard time dealing with other specializations in science. They further disclosed that although they can teach these disciplines, it is not guaranteed that it is up to the standards. In line with this, Dagasaan (2022), prompted the school officials that this concern requires a need for relevant training to bridge the gap of teaching outside of their field of expertise. According to Tirol (2022), coherence is met when teachers are specialized to teach a specific subject in science. It was further exemplified that if a teacher specializes in chemistry, they could teach it with or without a curriculum.

Overview of the science teachers' performance in Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Overall, the students and the school heads perceived the teachers' performance to be "high" as reflected in the overall weighted mean of 5.98 and 6.08, respectively. This result implies that science teachers have a quality display of strategies in content knowledge and pedagogy.

This "high" performance perceived by students and school heads indicates a strong foundation for effective science education delivery. The result of this study is in line with the findings of Rabano and Callo (2022) and Gepila (2020) that Secondary School teachers are highly proficient in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy.

Relationship Between the Teachers' Perception of The SPA in Science and their Performance

The result implies that the lesser the teachers' perception of the volatilities, the better their performance. This only shows that teachers are resilient and flexible to adopt abrupt changes in the educational system such as the implementation of SPA. Meanwhile, the table also shows that the perceptions of the teachers in terms of uncertainties ($p = 0.423$), complexities ($p = 0.937$), and ambiguities (0.627) of the SPA in Science are not significantly related to their performance.

The result can be attributed to several factors such as teachers' perception that learners' retention and mastery of topics and skills is not strengthened, and lack of necessary teaching and learning materials such as textbooks, ICT equipment, and laboratory equipment. It could also be linked to teachers' view that the approach lacks continuity of content since there is no constant repetition, review, and reinforcement of learning. It is important to remember that the more challenges the teacher encounters, the lesser their efficacy, resulting in low performance (Liu et al., 2022).

Teachers' perception that learners lack retention and mastery of the topic could factor into the teachers' motivation in teaching because they may feel frustrated if their efforts are not generating the desired outcomes and may result in teachers second-guessing in terms of other effective strategies that they can use in teaching. According to Sasmito et al. (2020), teachers who have low self-efficacy tend to have decreased motivation and a narrowed perspective in teaching. On the other hand, if the teachers have high self-efficacy, they persist in times of failure, are resilient in facing setbacks in the process (Bug-os et al., 2021), and are more open to scoping out new teaching methods (Lazarides & Warner, 2020).

Furthermore, this result could also be linked to teachers' view that the approach lacks continuity of content since there is no constant repetition, review, and reinforcement of learning. Because of this, there is a disruption in teaching plans as teachers are forced to spend more time in reviews of previous lessons before tackling the current competencies. This is due to some inconsistencies in the spiral progression approach in following the principles of sequencing of contents from one year level to the next. Thus, Perez et al. (2020) found that public school teachers view spiral progression as time-consuming because of the seeming repetition of topics across grade levels.

This result suggests that their perceptions of the aforementioned areas cannot account for their performance. This further implies that while understanding and addressing these aspects of the SPA are important for curriculum development and teacher support, these may not directly impact teaching outcomes. The teachers' experiences related to the uncertainties, complexities, and ambiguities in the SPA do not hinder their ability to facilitate learning; rather, these show their ability to adapt to and overcome challenges.

According to Gonzalez (2019), teachers overcome the challenges brought about by the spiral progression in science by reading more and browsing various sources for concepts that they need to teach. Meanwhile, others claimed to have sought assistance from co-teachers they deemed more knowledgeable of the content. These practices demonstrate the teachers' grit and perseverance to bridge the gap between current knowledge and the desired outcomes, which follows the concept of ZPD by Vygotsky, unlocking tasks beyond the current abilities through the aid of someone more knowledgeable (Margolis, 2020).

Conclusions

Despite their admission of the perceived challenges posed by the volatilities, uncertainties, complexities, and ambiguities (VUCA) of the spiral progression in science curriculum, science teachers have demonstrated resilience, adaptability, and dedication in their teaching approach. The fact that teachers affirmed a "somewhat agree" perception of these challenges suggests their awareness and acknowledgment of the difficulties inherent in the curriculum. However, their ability to navigate through these challenges effectively is reflected in the positive evaluation of their performance given by both students and school heads. This indicates that despite the VUCA of SPA in science, the teachers have managed to maintain quality instruction, showcasing their commitment to quality teaching, and the learning process.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following are hereby recommended:

1. To the school administrators, the conduct of training and workshops in teaching other branches of science offered in the spiral progression, especially in chemistry and physics to sustain the high level of teachers' competence in delivering instructions may be included in their faculty development plan.
2. To the junior high school teachers handling science, strategies like team teaching for subjects outside of specialty can be utilized. Second, teachers may attend comprehensive training in specialized fields (Chemistry and Physics) to be competent in teaching the different areas of SPA. Lastly, teachers may further attend training, especially on strategies to teach the spiral progression in science to lessen their perception of its volatilities.
3. To the Education Program Supervisor in Science, a regular evaluation of the VUCA of SPA should be done to bridge the gaps in the implementation.
4. To future researchers, a qualitative research design should be employed to understand more about the teachers' perception of the volatilities, uncertainties, complexities, and ambiguities on the spiral progression in science.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers secured an accomplished parental consent form in addition to the standard informed consent written in the questionnaire itself since the study would involve students as respondents. The researcher put extra care into dealing with the data given by the respondents to ensure dignity and privacy. Throughout the study, the researcher followed all the necessary protocols stipulated by the Ethics Committee of Foundation University to make sure the research topic was significant, evidently sound, and ethically correct. The authors declared that they have no conflicts of interest as far as this study is concerned.

Acknowledgements

The researcher is grateful to everyone who extended their time and effort in the completion of this study. Special thanks to Dr. Antonia Gueyndoline B. Despojo, the researcher's adviser, whose guidance made this study possible, and heartfelt appreciation to Dr. Romario P. Ybañez, Dr. Erlinda N. Calumpang, Dr. Sofia A. Tundag, Dr. Yvonne P. Cruz, and Dr. Cristina C. Calisang for their intellectual suggestions and advice. To Dr. Maria Chona Z. Futralan, the Statistician, the researcher is beyond grateful for your insights. Gratitude is also extended to Dr. Maria Trinidad V. Uy, Dr. Ben Jofil B. Diego, and Dr. Joselito S. Marabe for their assistance in validating the research instruments. The researcher also acknowledges the authors of various research works from which the indicators were adapted, as well as the respondents for their participation. Appreciation is also given to Dr. Bernadette A. Susvilla and Dr. Nilita L. Ragay for their approval to conduct the study. Additionally, the researcher thanks Ariel, Stephen, Gertrudes, and the rest of the family—for their continued support, unconditional love, and guidance. Lastly, to the late Juanito Cabrera Vaño Jr., you will always be an inspiration to the researcher.

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